

CORRELATION ANALYSIS OF EXTRAOCULAR MUSCLES AND INTRAOCULAR PRESSURE IN ENDOCRIN OPHTHALMOPATHY

Akhmedova S.M.1, Yuldashov S.A.2, Bilalov E.N.3, Nozimov A. E.4

1Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor. Department of Human Anatomy and OSTA. Tashkent Medical Academy. Tashkent. Uzbekistan.

2PhD student. Department of Human Anatomy and OSTA.

Tashkent Medical Academy. Tashkent. Uzbekistan.

3Doctor of Medical Sciences, Professor. Head of the Department of Ophthalmology.

Tashkent Medical Academy. Tashkent. Uzbekistan.

4Doctor of Philosophy degree "PhD" of medical sciences, Republican specialized scientific and practical medical center of eye microsurgery. Tashkent. Uzbekistan.

Relevance: The scientific literature contains a lot of information about pathological processes in the organ of vision that occur simultaneously with EOP, but the results of studies on the relationship between intraocular pressure and EOM edema are lacking. Secondary glaucoma is a chronic, asymptomatic multifactorial disease, and the risk of developing this type of glaucoma is high against the background of EOP. Also, according to clinical studies, an increase in intraocular pressure has been found in a quarter of patients with EOP.

Purpose of the study: To determine the relationship between extraocular muscle thickening and increased intraocular pressure in patients diagnosed with endocrine ophthalmopathy.

Materials and Methods: The research involved 72 patients (n=144 eyes) diagnosed with endocrine ophthalmopathy at the Fergana branch of the Republican Specialized Scientific and Practical Medical Center of Endocrinology, named after Academician Y.Y. Turaqulov. All patients had both eyes affected by EO. The study included 54 women and 18 men, aged between 20 and 71 years, with an average age of 44.8 ± 1.4 years. All patients underwent general ophthalmological examinations (visometry, ophthalmoscopy, biomicroscopy, gonioscopy using the Goldman three-lens, Maklakov tonometry and Hertel exophthalmometry). Patients also underwent biometry of extraocular muscles at a distance of 6-8 mm from the sclera using Accutome B-ScanPlus (USA). The ultrasound examination was performed using a device. A voltage range of 10 to 65 dB was used to obtain two-dimensional 2D images.

Research result: During the study, secondary glaucoma on the background of EOP was detected in 26 (36%) patients. The diagnosis of secondary glaucoma was made on the basis of gonioscopy data, namely neovascularization in the anterior chamber angle, dystrophic changes in the root of the iris and trabecular meshwork. This, in turn, occurs due to long-term hormonal therapy and an increase in the volume of retrobulbar tissues. The diagnosis of stage I glaucoma was confirmed in 14 patients, and stage II in 12. However, stages III and IV of glaucoma were not detected during the study. Normal intraocular pressure was detected in 56 patients (n=78%) (18.4 ± 4.55 mm Hg). Increased intraocular pressure (more than 26.0 mm Hg) was detected in 14 patients (n=22%) and antihypertensive therapy was recommended for them. According to the results of the analysis, a moderate positive correlation was found between the studied indicators (extraocular muscle s' echographic examination and IOP results) by Pearson correlation ($R = 0.38$; $P = 0.001$), which statistically reliably confirms the correlation of the study results.

Conclusion: In patients with endocrine ophthalmopathy, the risk of developing secondary glaucoma can be determined by simultaneous ultrasound diagnosis of extraocular muscles and assessment of intraocular pressure. This is one of the additional criteria for the diagnosis of secondary glaucoma developing in EOP and can be widely recommended for use in clinical practice for the treatment of complications of EOP.